

Identifiers, Identification Process, and Citation:

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Abstract:

We might find automatic updates, in our profiles, for our publications, that we do publish in various Journals or Archives. Being automatic based on identity, would allow us to deposit published materials in raw form, and that would lack proper citation. In this paper, we shall attempt to discuss, for automatic listing of our manuscripts in profiles as per Identifiers, either be in raw form or in published form.

Introduction:

Either it be Orcid, Pubmed, IEEE or any such identifiers, or identifiers as well as publishers, where we do have user profiles, and can list our publications, we shall begin with discussion of identifiers, and shall talk about Orcid, as it is found to be popular. My Orcid identifier registration number is 0000-0001-7796-7971.

Generally, below the title, name of author, their affiliations, and Orcid id can be found in papers, which might not be new topics to authors and publication community.

Now, let us begin with example of author's own Orcid and this very particular paper. I haven't mentioned my Orcid id in top, where in general, along with Institutional affiliation Orcid id was supposed to be written.

Discussion:

What would happen if I would write my Orcid id along with the place of my affiliation, and my name as author name? Answer would be nothing.

By means of Orcid id, when provided as hyperlink, or link, any readers would be able to see my Orcid Profile. Until the paper is published, (for an example this paper), it wouldn't be found in ORCID. And after publication too, if by means of link of Orcid profile, our papers are listed in my orcid profile,

citation wouldn't been found, until and unless, publishers themselves provide citation formats, which are found being talked as "Download citations".

That would mean, if we would write a program, or do programming and coding, then orcid profile id, and such identifiers, would be needed, then citation, when are included, so that, not only in Orcid, but in all identifiers, profiles, either by means of downloaded citation formats, like as APA, MLA, Harvard, Bibtext, would provide automated listing in our profile.

For an example: Let us discuss a program:

Find (numbers are set of instructions in sequential form)

1. User Details
2. Find identifier
3. Verify Identifier found
4. Use details of identifier found (Orcid, OID, DOI, Pubmed,.....)
5. Send data of identification (Between publisher and identifiers like as Orcid)
6. Collect Citation Details
7. Send citation details
8. Allow Feedback Option

Above Program lacks verification of user profiles, based on their citizenship, and verification process in instruction number 3 generally relies on profiles or emails, and these days, we can find claim papers, or questions can be found, "Is this paper authored by you?"

For such cases

we can add a instruction before user detail as

1. Verify Users

And that would need verification of user profiles, as per their identity, addresses and such topics, and we would have 9 instructions as:

1. Verify User

2. User Details
3. Find identifier
4. Verify Identifier found
5. Use Name of identifier found (Orcid, OID, DOI, Pubmed,.....)
6. Send data of identification (Between publisher and identifiers like as Orcid)
7. Collect Citation Details
8. Send citation details
9. Allow Feedback Option

In the above program, in instruction number 9, allow feedback option is provided, to discuss any errors, and for communication, though program would be less likely to have error, when details are accurate.

Features:

Since we have many of identifiers, our program needs to identify all such identifiers, so that we can send to all places at once, and two steps verification, based on identity like as citizenship, then verification of email are provided.

In instruction number 6, we have discussed, and have mentioned about sending data of identification, and that is for raw and unpublished manuscript like as an example of getting ISBN number by providing book, or getting DOI number by submitting articles.

We haven't mentioned wait for response, as instructions, because of uncertainty. As per example, if ISBN number, DOI number are provided, then additional instruction would be needed after instruction 6; as 6. Wait for Response, and collect response when received

Then our instruction number 7, would be instruction number 8, and so on, instruction number 9 would be instruction number 10.

When citations details too are send, then, proper citation would be observed, because, as per Instruction 6, data sent would too have citation based on source of publication and further requirement of identifiers.

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